

Development and Validation of Multiple-Choice Test of the Geometry Part of Mathematics for Secondary Class

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Abstract *This study overviews development and validity of a pool of multiple-choice test items of geometry part of Mathematics for secondary level. A table of specifications was prepared and a pool of 48 multiple-choice type test items was developed from the test universe. The content validity and face validity of test items was determined with the help of a team of experts. Sample of the study was 488 students of class 10. After determining the validity and reliability through item analysis and quantitative and qualitative analysis of the test, it was concluded that 30 out of 48 items in the test were valid, reliable and suitable for measurement of the learning achievements in the course. Therefore, these items are useful in the boards of examinations for 9 class in Punjab (Pakistan).*

Key Words

Achievement Test,
Difficulty Power,
Discrimination Power,
Item Analysis, Reliability,
Validity

Introduction

The history of formal student achievement assessment starts in 1838 when American New York State started it as a test of truth. The period from 1840 to 1875 recognized numerous types of tests in the history of American educational testing. Formal oral testing was replaced by written examinations and written testing was replaced by standardized examinations (Clements, 2007). The tests of achievement have therefrom become a specific component of the oral and written examinations to confirm the learning and prescribed material (Donald, 2013). These tests have set of rules in the design of construction. Ideally, tests should be standardized and have their own norms for their interpretation of scores during analysis (Mullis et al., 2007).

The procedure of standardized tests is difficult, expensive and time-consuming task. Standard procedure includes; selection of universe of test, setting of testing objectives, decision about the items' format, preparation of table of specifications, item bank construction, validity determination of items, pilot testing of items, analysis of pilot testing data and improvement of defective/ poor items in the light of analysis of all items, final try out of improved items and analysis of final try out data (Roid, 2012). Item analysis can be analyzed qualitatively in terms of their content and appearance, which includes the construction of face and content validity. Quantitative analysis of test items includes the measurement of item difficulty, distractor effect and items discrimination. (Rudner, 2011). Quantitative Item analysis procedure includes evaluation of difficulty level, discrimination level and distractor effect of each item of the test (Runder, 2011). Item difficulty indicates the proportion of correct and incorrect responses regarding an item. (Hulin, Drasgow & Parsons, 2013). An item having difficulty range between 0.20 to 0.80 is considered suitable. Discrimination level of an item is quality of an item that explains the power of an item to differentiate between high achievers and low achievers (Kelly, 2014). Ideally, an item having discrimination power in upper positive limits is always appreciated and an item having statistical value of discrimination power minimum to 0.30 is suggested for rejection (Roid, 2012).

In general, development and validation of tests for use of teachers in education adopting a standardized procedure is taken difficult. The institutions do not have resources in the form of money, time and trained staff to develop valid and reliable tests that can be used for a specific period of time (Akhter & Bahoo, 2015; Akhtar, 2015; Munir, 2016). The procedure of change in curriculum also discourage evaluators to use teacher made tests. But, researchers in the field can

do this laborious job. Otherwise, testing organizations can hire such technical staff on payment that standardized tests can be provided in institutions to improve the quality of assessment. Therefore, the present study was conducted to develop and validate a pool of items for evaluation of learning achievement of students in the Geometrical part of mathematics for secondary class. This is helpful for examination authorities to select some items for quality assessment of students.

Research Methodology

By purpose this study was research and development and by method this study followed the procedure of survey method in which standard procedure of test validation was adopted. In this study; text book of mathematics for 9th class; English medium taught in Punjab province was used for construction of tests items. Test items covered first three levels of cognitive domains and was administered to 10th class at the start of commencement of classes in new session.

Population and Sampling

All students of 10th grade of English medium schools in Punjab province were the population of the study. A sample of 488 students from 20 schools of Punjab province in Pakistan was taken by using simple random sampling technique. Ninety-six students participated in pilot testing and 392 students participated in final tryout of test.

Instrument of the study

This study comprised a multiple-choice type test of Geometry and this test was used as instrument for data collection in the study. The steps in the development of the test were as follow:

1. Text book of Mathematics for secondary level 9th published by Punjab Text Book Board Lahore was consulted. All nine chapters (9 to 17, PP.168 to 267) of geometry part of mathematics were defined as the universe of the test.
2. A table of specification was prepared. It was delimited to first three levels of Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive domains.

Table 1. Table of Specifications of Items

Chapter No.	Knowledge (Item no)	Comprehension(Item no)	Application (Item no)	Total
9	33	2, 34	3, 4	05
10	5	13, 32	35, 47	05
11	9, 29	12, 30	8, 21, 25	07
12	36, 46	41	10, 14	05
13	6, 37, 39	11, 23, 26	7, 38	08
14	22, 48	Nil	40	03
15	1, 16	15	27, 42	05
16	17, 20, 28	18	19, 31	06
17	24	43	44, 45	04
Total	17	13	18	48

3. Following the rules of development of multiple-choice items, 48 items with four options were prepared.
4. To examine the content validity of the test items three subject experts were approached. They were teaching this subject from at least 10 years and had M. Sc mathematics with M. Ed level qualification. To analyze the face validity of test, a team of two experts having Ph. D degree in educational assessment were chosen. Researchers sorted out poor items following the evaluation of experts and improved them according to suggestions of experts.
5. Forty-eight multiple-choice type test items with four options were arranged in a test booklet form and required number of copies were prepared. Researchers administered test booklets in examination conditions. The students were given open time to solve the test. Average time taken by students was 90 minutes in both trials.
6. Scoring of answer books was done by the researchers. Each correct response was given one mark. Zero mark was fixed for wrong answers.
7. Item analysis criteria was decided (see table 2) and each item of the test was analyzed on the basis of data. None of the rejected items of pilot test was included in final test. All revisions of items were incorporated

keeping in view their defects pointed out in item analysis, and improved items were again included in the final test.

Table 2. Item Analysis Criteria of the Test

Item's Interpretation	Item Analysis Criteria		
	Difficulty Power	Discrimination Power	Distractor Effect
Selected item	0.20-0.80	0.30 and above	At least 2% response on each option
Needs Revision	0.20 – 0.80	0.20 – 0.29	Any distractor had less than 2% response
Rejected item	Below 0.20	Below than 0.20	Below than 2% response on option

Results and Discussion

Item Analysis of the Test

Item analysis was done in two steps; item analysis of pilot testing data and item analysis of final try-out testing data. For understanding and comparison, results of pilot and final tryout are detailed in table 3.

Table 3. Item Analysis Results of Pilot and Final Try out Data

Pilot try-out results								Final try-out results							
Item	ρ	D	Distractor effect of options in %				Rm	Item	ρ	D	Distractor effect of options in %				Rm
	N=96	N=96	A	B	C	D		N=392	N=392	A	B	C	D		
1	0.38	0.58	58*	18	11	13	S	1	0.37	0.57	57*	10	22	11	S
2	0.42	0.53	20	10	17	53*	S	2	0.42	0.52	14	23	11	52*	S
3	0.37	0.62	08	09	62*	21	S	3	0.39	0.59	11	07	59*	23	S
4	0.27	0.59	28	11	02	59*	N R	4	0.23	0.55	24	15	06	55*	N R
5	0.32	0.57	06	24	57*	13	S	5	0.32	0.56	21	13	56*	10	S
6	0.42	0.59	14	59*	11	16	S	6	0.43	0.56	13	56*	09	22	S
7	0.35	0.58	58*	12	16	14	S	7	0.34	0.55	55*	10	06	29	S
8	0.43	0.62	18	62*	13	07	S	8	0.13	0.32	48	32*	13	07	R
9	0.40	0.61	04	16	61*	19	S	9	0.43	0.57	17	21	57*	05	S
10	0.37	0.59	21	59*	07	13	S	10	0.42	0.54	13	54*	14	19	S
11	0.32	0.55	55*	25	13	07	S	11	0.37	0.58	58*	12	19	11	S
12	0.28	0.49	49*	21	28	02	N R	12	0.27	0.46	46*	19	20	15	N R
13	0.41	0.54	06	54*	22	18	S	13	0.18	0.49	11	49*	13	27	R
14	0.34	0.50	50*	10	14	16	S	14	0.42	0.52	52*	12	10	26	S
15	0.41	0.65	12	08	65*	15	S	15	0.37	0.60	15	13	60*	12	S
16	0.25	0.61	61*	02	19	18	N R	16	0.19	0.41	41*	02	39	18	R
17	0.42	0.58	12	58*	14	16	S	17	0.37	0.52	20	52*	10	18	S
18	0.19	0.50	50*	34	07	09	R	18							
19	0.24	0.60	60*	20	02	18	N R	19	0.24	0.52	52*	18	11	19	N R
20	0.41	0.55	11	17	57*	15	S	20	0.37	0.51	14	13	51*	22	S
21	0.46	0.62	62*	11	13	14	S	21	0.35	0.53	53*	21	17	09	S
22	0.18	0.55	12	11	55*	22	R	22							
23	0.47	0.61	07	18	14	61*	S	23	0.37	0.51	13	19	17	51*	S
24	0.24	0.60	60*	19	20	11	S	24	0.24	0.40	40*	16	19	25	N R
25	0.17	0.49	49*	07	29	15	R	25							
26	0.43	0.66	14	10	66*	10	S	26	0.43	0.59	19	16	59*	06	S
27	0.29	0.60	60*	20	02	18	N R	27	0.11	0.10	10*	70	02	18	R
28	0.41	0.61	17	12	61*	10	S	28	0.37	0.58	16	17	58*	09	S
29	0.46	0.59	10	22	09	59*	S	29	0.36	0.50	15	21	14	50*	S
30	0.47	0.64	19	64*	08	09	S	30	0.45	0.60	17	60*	18	05	S
31	0.25	0.49	49*	21	28	02	N R	31	0.26	0.52	52*	15	20	13	N R
32	0.37	0.53	09	11	27	53*	S	32	0.42	0.56	12	17	15	56*	S
33	0.33	0.53	53*	27	18	02	N R	33	0.23	0.45	45*	19	23	13	N R
34	0.14	0.59	11	21	59*	09	R	34							
35	0.37	0.65	11	09	15	65*	S	35	0.37	0.61	13	14	12	61*	S
36	0.46	0.62	07	62*	23	18	S	36	0.36	0.53	14	53*	20	13	S
37	0.24	0.58	58*	22	18	02	N R	37	0.29	0.54	54*	17	19	07	N R
38	0.42	0.62	08	62*	10	20	S	38	0.42	0.59	16	59*	14	11	S
39	0.14	0.59	11	21	59*	09	R	39							
40	0.47	0.52	06	52*	18	24	S	40	0.37	0.43	16	43*	26	15	S
41	0.44	0.50	23	10	17	50*	S	41	0.44	0.47	19	11	23	47*	S
42	0.25	0.58	16	24	02	58*	N R	42	0.15	0.18	56	24	02	18*	R
43	0.47	0.61	13	07	61*	19	S	43	0.41	0.56	12	20	61*	07	S
44	0.33	0.40	40*	24	16	20	S	44	0.42	0.47	47*	17	11	25	S
45	0.27	0.37	23	37*	38	02	N R	45	0.17	0.17	43	17*	38	02	R
46	0.34	0.60	12	16	60*	12	S	46	0.44	0.59	10	11	59*	20	S
47	0.37	0.52	16	52*	09	23	S	47	0.47	0.56	09	56*	17	18	S
48	0.43	0.49	49*	19	12	20	S	48	0.43	0.43	43*	21	19	17	S

Note= * = Right options/ Key, ρ = Discrimination level, D = Difficulty level, Rm = Remarks, S = Selected item, R = Rejected item

Regarding the Pilot Testing

The table 3 demonstrates that 33 items were selected, 10 items needed revisions while 5 items were rejected. It showed that item numbers 18, 22, 25, 34 and 39 did not match the criteria of selection of items because their discrimination level was less than 0.20. So, these were rejected. On the other hand, the item numbers 4, 12, 16, 19, 24, 27, 31, 37, 42 and 45 had discrimination level between 0.20 to 0.29. So, these items were considered for revision. While other items match the criteria of selected items.

Regarding the Final Try out Results

The item numbers 18, 22, 25, 34 and 39 were rejected in pilot test. So, these serials numbers were left blank in the table of final try-out test. Similarly, the item numbers 4, 12, 16, 19, 27, 31, 33, 37, 42 and 45 were revised before final try-out test.

The part of final try out results in table 3 demonstrates that 30 items were selected, 7 items required revisions and 6 items were rejected. It showed that item numbers 8, 13, 16, 27, 42 and 45 did not match the criteria of selection of items. So, these items were rejected. On other hand, the item number 4, 12, 19, 24, 31, 33 and 37 had discrimination level greater than 0.20 but less than 0.30. Therefore, these items were needing revision for next try out. While other items matched the criteria of selection of items, so these were selected for future use.

Difficulty Index of the Final try out Items

Difficulty level of test play role in evaluation of quality of test. Analysis of difficulty level of the test (see table 4) exhibited that majority of items of the test were in middle difficulty range. A small number of test items (7%) were out of the range of decided criterion of difficulty range. These items were difficult for the respondents.

By comparing the quality of test with criterion of Kelly (2014), 93% of items in the test were in acceptable range and none of the item in test was easy item (0.71 to 1.00) because 93% items in the test were in the range of middle difficulty level i.e. 0.31 to 0.70 ((see table 4) and none of he items was very easy for the respondents.

Table 4. Distribution of Item Difficulty Index of final try out items

Difficulty Range	f	%
0.10 to 0.19	3	07
0.20 to 0. 29	0	00
0.30 to 0.39	1	02
0.40 to 0.49	9	21
0.50 to 0.59	27	63
0.60 to 0.61	3	07
Total	43	100

Discrimination Index of the Final try Out Items

Discrimination index of the items tried out in final exhibited that 70% of the items were meeting criterion of selected items. Moreover, all items were positively discriminating high achievers from low achievers (see table 5).

By comparing the results of this test regarding discrimination power of items with the criterion given by Roid (2012) about definition of quality of test items, this test has less (14%) number of poor items and some (16%) marginal items in discriminating high achievers to low achievers but majority of reasonably good or good items. He has elaborated that good items have a discrimination index of 0.40 and higher; reasonably good items from 0.30 to 0.39; marginal items from 0.20 to 0.29, and poor items less than 0.20.

Table 5. Distribution of Discrimination Power of Final try out Items

Discrimination Range	f	%
0.11 to 0.19	6	14
0.20 to 0.29	7	16
0.30 to 0.39	15	35
4.41 to 0.47	15	35
Total = 0.11 to 0.47	43	100

Reliability of the Test

Table 6. Summary of Reliability and Standard error of Measurement of Pilot and Final try out Results

Test Trial Stage	Sample	n	Variance	Σpq	SD	RT	SE
Pilot try out	96	48	145.62	11.611	12.06	0.93	3.19
Final try out	392	43	26.107	10.1951	5.11	0.62	3.15

Note: n= number of items in the test, RT= reliability of test applying formula KR 20, SE= standard error of measurement

Table 6 describes that reliability (using Kuder Richardson 20) of pilot try out data is good enough because acceptable reliability estimates ranging is considered from 0.856 to 0.958 (Wilson, 2005) and reliability in range of 0.832 to 0.931 is acceptable for the student, class and school environment scale in criterion defined by Popham (2005).

But, analysis of reliability of final try out data shows although acceptable but low (r= 0.62) in comparison to pilot try out data of the test. Analysis of literature regarding the reliability of tests indicates that value of correlation of teacher made test approximately 0.50 is accepted but nearly 0.60 is accepted and appreciated. According to Mohamad, et al (2015, p.165), although value of reliability close to most upper range (1.00) is good but in social sciences, value of correlation 0.60 is acceptable. But criterion described by Bahoo (2015) and Raza (2012) explains that a test having reliability in the range of 0.60 and 0.70 describes reliability of a test slightly low and needs to be supplemented by more trials. But, In the present study, standard error of measurement of pilot as well as final try out of data; 3.19 and 3.15 signifies a small piece of error in terms of raw scores in results that is evidence of better reliability of results.

Descriptive Analysis of Final Try-Out Test Score of the Examinees

Table 7. Statistical Analysis of Test Scores of final try out of Data

Try out	Total items	n	Range	Minimum score	Maximum score	Mean	Median	Mode	Skewness	Kurtosis
Pilot try out	48	096	40	06	46	27.29	30	15	-0.143	-1.34
Final try out	43	392	28	13	41	27.497	28	27	-0.193	-1.26

Table 7 shows value of range of data in final try out was less than of pilot try out. Analysis of scores of mean, median and mode explores that the test was difficult for the respondents and figure 1 and 2 exhibits that spread of scores of students was not exactly on normal distribution but near to normal in final distribution.

Figure 1. Spread of Scores of Pilot try out Data

Figure 2. Spread of Scores of Final try out Data

Gender and Locality Related Comparison of Scores of Students

Table 8. Gender and Locality wise Analysis of Final try out Data

Gender wise Analysis					Locality wise Analysis				
T- Test for Equality of Means					T- Test for Equality of Means				
Item	t	Sig	Mean Difference	SED	Item	t	Sig	Mean Difference	SED
1	-.201	.830	-.010	.049	1	-.835	.404	-.041	.049
2	.499	.618	.025	.050	2	-.195	.845	.010	.050
3	-.222	.825	-.011	.051	3	-.432	.666	-.022	.052
4	.490	.619	-.024	.049	4	1.466	.143	.072	.049
5	.094	.925	.005	.050	5	.648	.517	.033	.050
6	.425	.671	.022	.051	6	.769	.442	.039	.051
7	-.161	.871	-.008	.051	7	.567	.571	.029	.051
8	-.272	.786	-.014	.051	8	.349	.727	.018	.052
9	.985	.325	.050	.050	9	.445	.657	.023	.051
10	-1.33	.171	.071	.051	10	.228	.820	.012	.052
11	-.676	.499	-.034	.051	11	-.558	.577	.029	.051
12	-.534	.549	-.027	.051	12	.436	.663	.022	.051
13	.168	.876	.009	.051	13	-.101	.919	.005	.051
14	.081	.936	.004	.051	14	-1.05	.200	.050	.051
15	-.761	.447	-.037	.051	15	.180	.850	.010	.051
16	-1.03	.303	-.053	.048	16	-.060	.952	-.003	.051
17	-.318	.750	-.016	.050	17	-1.22	.203	-.065	.051
18	1.184	.237	-.060	.051	18	-1.33	.165	-.071	.051
19	-.367	.712	.019	.051	19	-1.98	.051	-.099	.051
20	-.024	.981	-.001	.050	20	-1.19	.234	-.060	.051
21	.597	.551	-.031	.051	21	-1.34	.178	-.069	.051
22	.324	.746	.016	.050	22	-1.02	.285	-.054	.050
23	.115	.909	.006	.050	23	-1.28	.201	-.065	.050
24	-.040	.968	.002	.051	24	-1.18	.236	-.060	.051
25	-.283	.771	-.014	.051	25	-.811	.418	-.041	.051
26	.340	.733	.017	.051	26	.860	.390	.044	.051
27	.028	.978	.001	.050	27	.740	.460	.037	.051
28	1.205	.229	.061	.051	28	.363	.784	.014	.051
29	-1.18	.239	-.059	.050	29	.360	.717	.018	.050
30	-.197	.844	-.010	.051	30	.945	.345	.041	.051
31	.187	.856	-.009	.050	31	.740	.460	.037	.051
32	.202	.840	.010	.051	32	.315	.753	.016	.051
33	.843	.400	.043	.050	33	-1.56	.118	-.079	.051
34	.306	.760	.009	.050	34	.611	.542	.031	.051

35	.080	.937	.004	.050	35	.152	.879	.008	.050
36	.997	.319	.050	.051	36	-.142	.887	-.007	.051
37	.322	.747	.016	.051	37	.024	.981	.001	.051
38	-.531	.599	-.029	.050	38	-.436	.661	-.022	.051
39	.099	.921	.005	.051	39	-.184	.854	-.009	.051
40	-1.16	.245	-.059	.051	40	.816	.412	.042	.051
41	1.184	.237	.060	.051	41	-.142	.887	-.007	.051
42	-.821	.412	-.041	.051	42	-.310	.757	-.016	.051
43	-.549	.584	-.028	.051	43	1.208	.228	.061	.050
44	.597	.537	.030	.050	44	.521	.603	.027	.051
45	-.785	.433	-.039	.051	45	-.953	.341	-.048	.050
46	-.747	.455	-.031	.050	46	.154	.878	.008	.050
47	.943	.346	-.048	.051	47	-.808	.419	-.041	.051
48	-.442	.658	-.023	.051	48	.390	.698	.020	.052
Total	-.098	.922	-.052	.524	Total	.744	.457	.392	.526

Note: Sig \leq 0.05, n=392, SED= Standard Error of Difference

The table 8 revealed that the values of mean difference between boys and girls and rural and urban are nearly same regarding all items. Moreover, t test results indicate no significant mean difference between the test scores of groups.

Table 9. Comparison of Mean Scores of Students in Final Test Based on Gender and Locality

Locality	n	Mean	Gender	n	Mean
Urban	235	27.340	Male	229	27.476
Rural	157	27.732	Female	163	27.527
Total	392	27.497	Total	392	27.497

Table 9 describes comparison of mean difference of scores of rural versus urban and boys versus girls in whole test. It explains no big difference between performance of groups. This also explores that test was equally favorable for students on the bases of gender and locality.

Conclusion

It was found that all items were in the range of middle difficult in the final test. Discrimination level of 5 items in pilot study and 6 items in final try-out was less than the criteria of the selection of items, so these eleven items were rejected. Thirty items of the test met the criteria of the selection of items. It was found that the mean score of final test was 27.497, its median was 28, the mode was 27, while the standard deviation of test was 5.11. It was found that the value of standard error of measurement was low and it indicated that the test has very low chance of error in results. The reliability of test was 0.93 for pilot try out but 0.62 for final try out data, that showed that test was reliable but needs more experimentation of testing on the samples. It was concluded that all test items had positive discrimination level. It was also concluded that the scores of students in final test were although not exactly but near to normal distribution.

Recommendations

The study recommended that 30 selected items became the basis for standardization of an achievement test of geometrical part of secondary level mathematics. These items may be used in further researches on other samples. The board of secondary examinations may select these items for the board examinations.

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